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God-Fatherism And Its Influence On Nigerian Politics And Politicians In Rivers State Nigeria, 2015-2023

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzed god-fatherism and its influence on Nigerian politics and politicians in Rivers State Nigeria. The objective of the study is to; find out whether Money politics has affected politics and politicians in Rivers State, Nigeria; examine the effect of binding of godsons on the politics and politicians in Rivers State, Nigeria; determine the extent Political Rascality affected politics and politicians in Rivers State, Nigeria. Three research hypothesis and three research questions are formulated in line with the above objectives of the study. Descriptive survey design method was used; the sample techniques employed simple random sampling. The study selected one LG from each senatorial zone to avoid bias result and to make sure every quarters of River state are represented, the population are 257422 where the sample size is 399 using Taro Yamane formula. The researcher distributes Three hundred and ninety-nine (399) questionnaires but only three hundred and forty-seven (347) copies of questionnaire were retrieved. Structured questionnaire were use to gather information from the population. Percentage tables and ANOVA method of data analysis was used to test the questionnaire. The finding of the study shows that Money politics has significant effect on politics and politicians in Rivers State, Nigeria; Binding of godsons has significant effect on the politics and politicians in Rivers State, Nigeria; Political Rascality has significant effect on politics and politicians in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study recommends that Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) should adopt the use of e-voting for all elections in the country to curtail electoral scam. The electoral laws in Nigeria should be reformed to mitigate the funding of political parties and their candidates by individuals and corporate organizations. Elections in Nigeria continue to suffer wanton abuses and gross violation of its sanctity.

Keywords: god-fatherism, Money politics, binding of godsons, Political Rascality, politicians

1.1 INTRODUCTION

God-fatherism in Nigeria has been the hallmark of Nigeria politics, West African countries and other developing countries around the globe (Azeez, 2014). The political class's struggle to take control of political and economic power in the society and institutions is influenced by the control of wealth and social status; this struggle, and the resulting ideals, have had a important effect on society in a variety of ways. In our existing democratic experience, power tussles among members of the political class have metamorphosed in political violence in various forms and ways in our ever transforming democratic history (Osakede & Ijimakinwa, 2016).

The politics of god-fatherism has featured prominently in the political history of independent Nigeria. The problems arising from god-fatherism are myriad and it is one of the greatest glitches facing the Nigerian political system. The problem is such that the god-son oftentimes is a stooge of the godfather and he that “pays the piper dictates the tune” (Edigin, 2010). The failure of the god-son to meet the demands of the god-father is often punished with impeachments or denial of re-election. With the return to democratic rule in 1999, the country witnessed a heightened tempo in the politics of god-fatherism. The politics of god-fatherism has eaten deep into the political movements of many nations, including Nigeria. The politics of god-fatherism has become part and parcel of the political condition of actualizing the political dreams of the contestants in the state (Ezeamama, Orji, and Obani, (2024).

Several problems were identified as a source of politics of god-fatherism. The central argument is that in the Rivers State politics “god-fatherism” has become the key or pillar to many politicians to win election. This is because many contenders cannot contest and win even for a single term, without the influence of the Godfather. But because of the influence of the godfathers many people are contesting and winning the election at all cost, because of the power of the godfathers. This problem of godfathers is extensively practiced in all parts of the country, including Rivers State, it is observed that to contest for any political post it has become necessary to have strong political godfather before considering and run for any elective offices or even political appointment (Ezeamama, 2019).

This has created a wide vacuum among the contestants and the state at large, because those without the godfathers cannot contest for any post. It is understood that all the positions won because of the influence of godfathers cannot yield positive development (Ezeamama & Orji, 2024). This is because the political elites asked contestants to sign an agreement to ensure that they agree with all the promises that they had entered with the elites. The contestant makes sure that all the money spends on him during the election were paid completely with interests. This led to political crisis between the aspirants and the godfathers, by extension among the citizens in the state or constituency (Ezeamama & Obani, 2024). This crisis has created a wide gap in the socioeconomic development of the state. For instance, if the godfathers sponsor a candidate into an elective position, such as governor, or president, then he has the power and right to recommend for commissioners or ministers for a political position into the cabinet and to request for exaggerated contracts (Ezeamama and Ofozoba 2023). Given this, the study merit to examine god-fatherism and its influence on Nigerian politics and politicians in Rivers State Nigeria.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine god-fatherism and its influence on Nigerian politics and politicians in Rivers State Nigeria. Specifically, this study seeks to:

1. To find out whether Money politics has affected politics and politicians in Rivers State, Nigeria?
2. To examine the effect of binding of godsons on the politics and politicians in Rivers State, Nigeria
3. To determine the extent Political Rascality affected politics and politicians in Rivers State, Nigeria?

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Theoretical Framework

The work is anchored on elite theory

Elite Theory

This study adopts elite theory in examining the overbearing influence of god-fatherism on Nigerian nascent democratic experiences. Vilfredo Pareto developed the theory in 1935. The supposition of the theory is that power is rotated among the elites at the expense of the masses or electorates. As Pareto argued, the political elites insulate and isolate themselves from their society and try as much as possible to reproduce themselves from within. They do all possible within their reach to ensure that non-elites do not

join their membership. To ensure this, the political elites maintain a safe, functional distance from the rest of the society.

They reproduce themselves on an individual and selective basis in a process, which Pareto specifically referred to as the 'circulation of elites'. The criteria for such elite recruitment are often parochial and the process is usually done in a manner that does not in any way compromise the traditional integrity of the dominant elite class. Pareto further argued that the dominant class often tries to frustrate any efforts at the 'collective circulation of elites' and would rather support individual recruitment. However, Mosca (1939) disagrees with Pareto that elite recruitment is only possible on an individual basis. He believes in the possibility of one social class replacing another and posited that it is possible for a non-elite member to join the elite class through 'collective social mobility'.

This refers to the status that people attain because of their social, economic and professional efforts. Mosca also believes that there exists already in many societies of the world a group of people that could be referred to as 'sub-elite'. These people facilitate communication between the elite and the non-elite and are thus potential tools for relatively large-scale elite recruitment. This argument makes it possible for both sub-elite and non-elite to become recruited into the political elite class in Nigeria. The elite theory sees elites as players governing the state and national resources, and occupying key positions related to power networks. Thus, the perception of elite class is more carefully connected to "the Weberian knowledge of power, understood as the competence of executing one's will, even against the will of the general populous" God-fatherism serves as a medium for such selective elite recruitment in Nigeria. The resultant effects of the above in Nigeria polity are under-development, abject poverty, acute youth unemployment, poor health prospects and misinterpretation of what politics ought to be.

Relevance of the theory to the study

The relevance of the elite theory to this paper is based on its ability to justify how the transition of people into the political elite class is facilitated by politics of god-fatherism. Liberalism, as we have experienced in Nigeria, promotes extreme elitist democracy and money-inspired electioneering system, leaving the masses as 'onlooker' and keep denying Nigerians the much-needed institutional, socio-economic and political advancement. The elite theory is very much concerned with structures, especially authority structure. It is based on the assumption that elite action has a causal effect on the relationship between the state and society since the elites have greater influence/control of the state than the masses.

According to Mosca (1939), elite theory points to the concentration of power in the hands of a minority group which 'perform all political functions, monopolizes power and enjoys the advantages that power brings'. Thus public policy may be viewed as the value and preferences of governing elites. The Nigerian polity represents a situation where the welfare of the citizenry is grossly mortgaged for the interests of a few politicians and their mentors (godfathers). The electorates are impoverished the more, and the corrupt rich godfathers are enriching themselves the more.

2.2 Empirical Review

Ishaka, Mohammed, & Angulu (2022), studied the implication of politics of godfatherism on the socio-economic and political development of Nigeria. Obviously, godfatherism has permeated every fabric of the country and has seriously affected the political system. This paper is qualitative in nature; data were obtained from secondary sources where numerous articles, newspapers, magazines, books reports, and archives were systematically reviewed. In elucidating the topic under examination, the researcher used Elite theory. This theory was advocated by Vilfredo Pareto in 1935. The postulation of the theory is that elites are replaced by another group of elites, meaning that the majority are unavoidably governed by the minority. The study found that the politics of godfatherism has a negative impact on the socio-economic and political development of the nation by confining power in the hands of the few elites at the expense of the masses (electorates). This has affected the socio-economic and political development of the nation, and by extension led to inter-party and intra-party defections, decampings and conflicts among the party members. Therefore, the study recommends the implementation of the direct primary election in selecting

candidates into elective positions. In addition to that, INEC should make a law that will discourage money politics and should as well punish culprits involved in such an illegal political act Igbini & Okolie, (2020). Examined the Godfatherism and its threat to the Nigeria's Nascent Democracy. Democracy has promoted political and socio-economic development far more effectively than any other political system across many countries and centuries of history. In Nigeria, it has been characterized with political corruption, ethnic politics, politicking of core government policies and programmes and politics of godfatherism. Since the return of democratic rule in 1999 to date, the country witnessed a heightened tempo in the politics of godfatherism, which has not only retards the process of democratic consolidation but also undermines effective state governance and restricts rather than broadens democratic representation. Godfatherism is one of the greatest glitches facing the Nigerian political system. This paper therefore, attempts a reflection on the nature, causes and effect of godfatherism on Nigeria's nascent democracy. We anchored our investigation on some basic propositions arising from the elite theory and argue that politics of godfatherism negates peaceful coexistence, law and order and poses a threat to the Nigeria's nascent democracy. This paper which is theoretical in nature draws its argument basically from secondary data which include journal articles, textbooks and internet sources. Requisite conclusion and recommendations were provided in the light of the theoretical findings

Nwambuko, Uchechukwu, and Omiunu (2024) examined the politics of godfatherism and democratic governance in Nigeria with preference to Rivers State political crisis. The objectives of the study were to identify the environmental factors influencing the politics of godfatherism in Rivers State; to examine the impact the politics of godfatherism has on democratic governance in Rivers State; and to find out strategies to abate politics of godfatherism in Rivers State. The study adopted the elite theory, applied a descriptive survey research design, used both primary and secondary sources of data and a structured questionnaire as the instrument for data collection was employed. The population of the study is 5,198,716 residents in Rivers State (National Population Commission of Nigeria, 2006). The sample population is 400 (derived via the application of Taro Yamani sample size determination formula). The data collected via questionnaire were analyzed using table and percentages, while the hypotheses were tested using the chi-square. The findings of the study revealed that there are environmental factors inciting politics of godfatherism in Rivers State; that politics of godfatherism has adversely impacted on democratic governance in Rivers State; and that there are strategic measures to abate politics of godfatherism in Rivers State. Based on the findings, the study recommended the prevention of undue influence from political godfathers, enforcement of campaign finance regulations, promotion of a level playing field for all candidates before and during elections in Nigeria among others.

Edigin (2022) Political Conflicts and Godfatherism in Nigeria: A Focus on the Fourth Republic. The conflict arising from godfatherism has become one of the greatest problems facing the Nigerian political system. The holder of the political position becomes a stooge to his godfather because he that pays the piper dictates the tune. By the time the godson refuses to meet their (godfathers) demand, he is eventually impeached from political office. In Nigerias fourth republic dispensation (1999 till date), the Saraki-Lawal face off, Nwobodo Nnamani quagmire, Adedibu Ladoja crisis, Uba-Ngige saga and all other godfathers protg crises in Nigeria do not only portray great danger to our democratic experiments, but also on the very essence and validity of our existence as a nation. The billions of naira expended by Nigerian godfathers for bankrolling the elections of their godsons have totally monetized elections in Nigeria which automatically disqualifies men of honour, character and integrity from holding elected public positions. The issue of godfatherism in Nigeria politics is as a result of societal decay, which has encroached into spheres of the Nigerian polity. It is therefore suggested that godfatherism should not be treated as a party affair, but should be offered political, social and legal treatment by the government and the stakeholders in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

3.1: Research Design

Cross sectional Survey research design was used in carrying out the study. Ikeagwu (1997) opined that studies of this nature will be survey method to look for information on facts, attitudes, practices and opinions of the respondents.

3.2: Sources of Data

The source of data collection for this research work was derived from two specific areas, the primary and the secondary sources. In this study, the data collection technique was based on questionnaire. The researcher developed the questionnaire that will be administered to the respondents.

3.3 Population of the Study

The population of the study is the youth of the selected local government area river State which is 257422 which comprised of three Local Government Areas each in the three senatorial zones (Rivers East, Rivers South East and Rivers West). In other words, a total number of 3 Local Government Areas out of 23 were selected for the study. The study selected one LG from each senatorial zone to avoid bias result and to make sure every quarters of Anambra state are represented.

The Population of Local Governments

	Senatorial zones	Unemployed youth
S/N	<u>Rivers East senatorial district</u>	
1	Obio-Akpor	75, 166
	<u>Rivers South East senatorial district</u>	
2	Opobo–Nkoro,	83, 014
	<u>Rivers West senatorial district</u>	
3	Asari-Toru,	99, 242
	Sub total	257,422

Source: Administration and General Services Department, 2024

3.5 Determination of Sample Size.

Taro Yamane formula will be used to determine the Sample size. The formula is given as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where

n= Sample size of the study=

N = Population

1 = Constant value

e = Error margin assumed to be (5%)

Applying this formula, we have

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{257422}{1+257422(5\%)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{257422}{1+257422 (0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{257422}{1+643.555}$$

$$n = \frac{257422}{644.555}$$

Sample size = 399.37941 apprx 399

The research adopts two sampling techniques, namely purposive sampling and stratified sampling. Purposive sampling enables the researcher to choose the respondents that were of interest to the study while the stratified random sampling permits each of the different respondents in all the different states to be selected without bias.

3.4: Method of Data Collection

The major research instrument adopted for the study is the uses of structured questionnaire to elicit responses for the sample population.

3.5: Method of Data Analysis.

In this study, the descriptive statistics such frequency counts with simple percentage were used to analyse bio – data of the respondents and the four research questions. At the inferential level of analysis, linear regression were used to test hypotheses 1, 2, 3, and 4 to determine the extent of correlation between x and y variables (Independent and Dependent). All analyses were done through the application of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS 20 windows)

PRESENTATION ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents the data obtained from the respondents through the administered questionnaire. Three hundred and ninety-nine (399) were administered among the employees of selected respondents. However, three hundred and forty-seven (347) copies of questionnaire were retrieved. Therefore, the analysis and interpretation of data were based on the returned questionnaire. The validity and reliability of this study is highly ensured, despite the number of questionnaires not returned. The method used was percentage table technique and t-test for the hypothesis.

4.1 Questionnaire Response Rate

Copies of Distributed	Copies of Returned	Percentage Returned
350	347	99.14

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.1: Respondents’ Demographic Variables

4.1.1 Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	172	49.4	49.6
	Female	175	50.3	100.0
	Total	347	99.7	100.0

Source: Field Survey 2025

The above table reveals that the one hundred and seventy-two of the respondents which represents 49.4 persons were male respondents, while one hundred and seventy-five (175) respondents which represent 50.4% were female respondents. By implication, female respondents were more than male respondents by 3 respondents in our selected sample for this study. The implication of this is to enable us to know the number of female and male that successfully returned their questionnaire

4.1.2 Marital Status

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Married	252	72.4	72.6	72.6
Valid Single	95	27.3	27.4	100.0
Valid Total	347	99.7	100.0	

Source: Field Survey 2025

In the table above, out of the three hundred and forty-seven (347) respondents, two hundred and fifty-two (252) of the respondents were married, while ninety-five (95) respondents which represent 27.4 percent are single. It is therefore glaring that the majority of the respondents are married as at the time of this study. Thus, marital status table help us to know the number of single, and married, respondents that answered the distributed questionnaire.

Table 4.1.3 level of Education

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid WAEC/NECO	29	4.4	4.7	8.6
Valid BSC/HND	157	22.6	45.2	41.7
Valid MSC/MBA	174	50.6	50.1	93.2
Valid Total	347	98.3	100.0	

Source: Field Survey 2025

The table above indicates that twenty-nine (29) respondents which representing 4.7% percent maintain to acquired WAEC OR NECO while 45.2% percent of the respondents which represents one hundred and fifty-seven (157) have BSC/HND. However, one hundred and seventy-four respondents which represent 50.1 percent either have MSC or MBA. This as the one of demographic item helps us to identify the education qualification of the respondents.

4.1.4 Age

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 18-25	29	9.1	9.6	9.6
Valid 26-33	118	22.9	34.2	33.8
Valid 34-40	104	32.6	29.9	68.2
Valid 41-50	28	8.8	9.3	77.5
Valid 51-above	68	21.3	19.5	100.0
Valid Total	347	94.7	100.0	

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.3 above depicted the age bracket of the respondents. The distribution shows that 9.6% of the respondents are between the age brackets of 18 to 25 years while 34.2% respondents are within the age bracket of 26-33 years. On the same note, 29.9% of the respondents are within the age bracket of 34 - 40 years. On the same note, 9.3% of the respondents are within the age bracket of 41 - 50 years, while the remaining respondents representing 19.5% are within the age bracket of 51 years and above.

4.2 Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One

Ho₁: Money politics has no significant effect on politics and politicians in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 4.2.1 ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6.911	4	1.382	38.82	.000 ^b
	Residual	80.589	343	0.2356		
	Total	87.500	347			

Source: SPSS, Version, 20 2025

However, from the Anova table above, it was observed that the probability value of hypothesis one is less than 0.05% level of significance (0.000), as a result null hypothesis will be rejected and alternative is accepted, meanwhile Money politics has significant effect on politics and politicians in Rivers State, Nigeria

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: Binding of godsons has no significant effect on the politics and politicians in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 4.2.2 ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	22.507	3	4.501	6.952	.002 ^b
	Residual	64.993	344	2.708		
	Total	87.500	347			

Source: SPSS, Version, 20 2025

However, from the Anova table above, it was observed that the probability value of hypothesis two is less than 0.05% level of significance (0.02), as a result null hypothesis will be rejected and alternative accepted, meanwhile Binding of godsons has significant effect on the politics and politicians in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three

Ho₃ Political Rascality has no significant effect on politics and politicians in Rivers State, Nigeria

Table 4.4.3 ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	20.154	3	4.031	15.236	.000 ^b
	Residual	67.346	344	2.806		
	Total	87.500	347			

Source: SPSS, Version, 20 2025

However, from the Anova table above, it was observed that the probability value of hypothesis three is less than 0.05% level of significance (0.000), as a result null hypothesis will be rejected and alternative accepted, meanwhile Political Rascality has significant effect on politics and politicians in Rivers State, Nigeria

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

The investigation of the god-fatherism and its influence on Nigerian politics and politicians in Rivers State Nigeria State was carried out using the ANOVA model developed to capture unemployment reduction as dependent on skill acquisition. The god-fatherism were proxied by Political Rascality, money politics, binding of godsons. The findings of the study showed as follows that:

1. Money politics has significant effect on politics and politicians in Rivers State, Nigeria
2. Binding of godsons has significant effect on the politics and politicians in Rivers State, Nigeria..
3. Political Rascality has significant effect on politics and politicians in Rivers State, Nigeria

5.2 Conclusion

It is true that political godfatherism is as old as democracy itself in Nigeria but in its present form, the phenomenon epitomizes corruption and criminality in electoral politics and governance. This scenario engenders political alienation and social exclusion. If this development is allowed to continue, the country's dream and aspiration to be among the 20 leading economies of the world by 2050 will be amirage and Nigeria will still be running on the same spot, experiencing a lot of motion without movement (Ake, 1981). This is why the fight against godfathers politics has become imperative because democracy is not a gift that can be gotten on a platter of gold. Genuine and enduring democracy everywhere is won through struggles by democrats and the civil society, and it is institutionalized through their vision and unwavering democratization. Nigerians who are concerned with deepening democracy and strengthening the capacity of democratic institutions, including strengthening the capacity of the Nigerian state to deliver the goods of good governance, confronting the gods of our polity is a war that must be fought, and must be won.

5.3 Recommendations

The following recommendations are posed based on the findings of the study:

1. Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) should adopt the use of e-voting for all elections in the country to curtail electoral scam. This will go a long way to reduce the elections rigging and well as well encourage the interest aspirants to vie for any position of their choice without pledging alliance to the godfathers for guaranteed winning ticket.
2. The electoral laws in Nigeria should be reformed to mitigate the funding of political parties and their candidates by individuals and corporate organizations. This will go a long way in abrogating the phenomenon of godfatherism and democracy will thrive in the country.
3. Elections in Nigeria continue to suffer wanton abuses and gross violation of its sanctity. The illegal use of soldiers and the police personnel to harass citizens, to entrench anarchy, to enthrone chaos where there is order, and to intimidate and brutalize opposition political candidate and their supporters must be discouraged and outlawed.

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